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Sources: Dixon, RMW. Boumaa Fijian

Questionnaire for Word Domains

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77 Boumaa Fijian

In many cases, refer to Bickel's Programm und Verzeichnis der verfügbaren Materialien web instructional modules for operational definitions (<http://www.uni-leipzig.de/~bickel/lehre/strukturkurs/teil1/index.html>)

Please include 1 or 2 examples (to the extent that they exist in the grammar) to illustrate processes.

If you are using multiple grammars/sources, please cite the specific source next to examples
Please check the Autotyp bibliography to see if a grammar has been used in a previous Autotyp analysis. If so, try to refer to that grammar first, and then choose others if necessary

In addition, if you are referring to a journal article, (as opposed to a reference grammar) it might be wise to consult with Balthasar, Tracy or Kristine first, to make sure the article is appropriate to use for this questionnaire.

I.

Segmental Properties

Describe phonotactic patterns and restrictions on both lexemes and grammatical morphemes. Describe the locations of these phenomena (e.g. syllable-final, initial...). If identifiable loanwords or other words are excluded, note this.

Describe phonological processes where reference is made to domains (special attention should be given to gemination, epenthesis, lengthening, vowel or cons. harmony)

What is the default syllable template for both lexemes and grammatical forms? Is there an explicitly stated minimal word requirements? (This may be stated in terms of obligatory vowel length or syllable structure in monosyllabic words) Do all morpheme types adhere to this requirement/follow this pattern? If not, note the differences.

Yes, a minimal word requirement—bimoraic/disyllabic. 2 types of bimora: diphthong and long vowel

no attested words longer than 8 morae

Looks like there are no c clusters in initial position

No initial /k/ unless English loan or from V (standard) dialect. In some V loans #k > #glottal stop

/f/ very peripheral, not word-initial, but if so only through loans

affricate /j/--not word initial unless through loans

looks like no final C's at end of word (but not sure if they occur word-internally)

No #V:C unless through English loans aapolo 'apple'

But you do get #VV oo 'cloud'; oi 'really'

No words: #VV.(C)V# unless the vowels are a diphthong. I guess this is just a fact about the language because it wouldn't necessarily interfere with stress patterns

Diphthongs are somewhat different from long vowels as they are realized as a single unit of a single heavy mora within a phonologically free unit, and they are realized (and resyllabified) as separate vowel segments across a boundary of 2 phonological units.

Are there super heavy syllables (SHS) in the language (e.g. V:C, VVC, VCC...) or trimoraics? If so, what are the restrictions of distribution (cf. Hall offprint for examples in English). For example, are SHS limited to final position in a word, initial, word-medial? If the author includes information on SHS as they relate to compounding or inflectional processes, please note this also (include examples)
no SHSyllables listed or evident in data

II.

Prosodic Properties

If stress is not explicitly discussed but is marked, where is primary stress located (initial, pre-final, final...), and is it a fixed system? What are the rhythmic patterns and what is the direction (e.g. trochee, iamb, unbounded)? To what constituents is stress attracted (V:, VV, VC, etc.)? Is it quantity sensitive?

Stress seems to be a primary cue for determining the number of pwords within a single (complex) gword

Stress rule: primary stress falls on the syllable with the 2nd mora from the end edge from a word. It falls on the syllable with the penultimate mora from end of pword. A long vowel or a diphthong must bear primary stress in the pword. A V has a single mora; a V: and VV are bimoraic. since long vowels and diphthongs are bimoraic, they must make the stress system happy, and one of these must be even numbered from the end of the pword.

We know that the following words are CV.CV(C).(V) in structure:

vu.'a-qu 'grandchild.1sg'

v'e.a 'soft, overripe breadfruit'

We know this because the vowels are not pronounced like diphthongs, and the main stress is restricted to the single vowel of the penult, and does not carry across both vowels. On a syllable with main stress, the main stress is perceived as a higher pitch.

Contrast the 2 words:

ma.t'u.a 'mature' (3 syllables, so only the u vowel gets the main stress/higher pitch)

ma.t'a'u 'stone axe' (2 syllable, so both vowels are part of diphthong and both take this main stress that sounds like a higher pitch)

More examples:

a) #t'a'u 'touch down'

#t'a'u-ca 'touch down on TRANS'

b) #l'u.a 'vomit'

#lu.'a-ca 'vomit TRANS'

the -ca suffix is part of the larger pword because it participates in the stress system . We can see this especially with the 2 examples in b) where -ca in the transitive construction forces a relocation of stress to the a vowel and not the u vowel. We also know that the monosyllabic form in b) is disyllabic because the primary stress is just on the u vowel and the 2 vowels are pronounced distinctly, not as a diphthong.

Stress not so much quantity sensitive as it is locationally sensitive.

Does stress serve any morpho-syntactic function? If so, explain.

Do stress demarcations highlight or illustrate morpheme boundaries across a morphologically complex word? Do different morphemes have different stress patterns?

Describe stress patterns with regard to compounding. Do prosodic rules apply across compounds, or are they restricted to internal position?

compounds: each element carries its own primary stress, following stress patterns of individual pwords

s'ara.van'u'a

If there is a tone system, what is the TBU (tone bearing unit)? Describe any external sandhi processes (any restrictions in sequential combinations of tones) and any other tone phenomena in morphologically complex forms (e.g. compounds, concatenations, phrasal constituents). Does tone serve a purely phonological function, or does it serve any morpho-syntactic function? The language may have a system of pitch accent or may be semi-tonal. In such cases, describe any relevant phenomena. Is there a system of contrastive phonation types (either as part of a tone system or individually)? If so, note any discussion of domain of different phonation types (either in combination with other tone cues like pitch or separately).

III.

Morpho-Syntax

Discuss the degree and types of fusion between morpheme boundaries. If there are differences between morphemes, please note this. Describe any non-adjacent allomorphy, or allomorphy that violates adjacency conditions or that goes across words. Refer to Bickel and Nichols chapter on inflectional morphology (<http://www.uni-leipzig.de/~bickel/research/papers/index.html>) for relevant terminology & definitions

ADDENDUM: Limit descriptions of allomorphy to major word classes (noun, verb). Also limit to inflectional allomorphy (no derivational, adjectival endings, adverbial, etc.). For example, conjugational NP or derivational verb allomorphy is relevant. Look for adjacency condtions

Is there any infixation, circumfixation or simulfixation? What are the patterns?

What reduplication patterns are described? What is copied (total vs. partial)? If reduplication is partial, is it described in terms of segmental sequences or prosodic units (e.g. the foot with specific restrictions, or in terms of a template)? In reduplication is there any segment mutation

(e.g. devoicing, vowel place-of-articulation change)? Does the resulting reduplicated form defy the default phonotactic or prosodic properties of the language?

Dixon says reduplication boundary is the phonological word boundary, and reduplication always results in 2 pwords.

'ilo > iloilo [i.lo] [i.lo] 2 pwords, each with 2 syllables, 2 main stresses

v'oi > v'o'i.v'o'i oi =diphthong and larger stress domain is copied, w/2 main stress resulting, 2 pwords

but'a?o 'to steal' > b'uta.but'a?o 'to steal repeatedly'

Describe the relevant distribution and phonological properties of clitics and particles. To what extent does the author describe them as phonologically bound or free? If they are free, are there still limitations in distribution, co-occurrence, the ability of other elements to be inserted between these and their "host" form? Please include examples.

Dixon says that if a grammatical word that is CV in structure does not enter into a pword combination with something else (and it has to do something because it cannot be a pword on its own--too small), then it cliticizes to an adjacent already-existing pword. But it does not participate in the stress rules--it is added on as an extra unstressed syllable. It doesn't take stress and does not contribute to the system either.

*me+dr'e'e 'should + pull' (note not *m'e.dree or *me.dr'e.e)*

Some pword combinations (made up of multiple gwords) are pretty selective and restricted. An example is the derivational prefix i-, which only coheres phonologically with a preceding common article.

IV.

Other Questions

Do unstressed vowels undergo any kind of reduction, and does this reduction have a specific domain (final edge, beginning edge, etc)? What happens to unbounded feet, and does this apply in all types of word-forms, or are there exceptions?

Describe word-word combinations (e.g. compounds, incorporation, complex predicates). Specifically, what types of phonological processes are involved in compounds that make them alike or different from mono-morphemic words, or multimorphemic inflectional forms? Look to cues like stress, tone, segmental changes, vowel changes, etc. Provide a couple of examples to illustrate the process.

Describe bipartite stems (read the relevant discussion in the inflectional morphology chapter).

Periphrastic morphology: state which forms are formed peripherally and what the general template is (e.g. Aux + Stem; Aux + inflected form; Aux + Particle; Aux + Converb).

In periphrastic constructions, what are the ordering possibilities of forms? Describe also any restrictions noted on what other elements (if any) may intervene between or co-occur with periphrastic forms. Also, describe any special inflectional marking possibilities or restrictions that may occur in periphrastic constructions (e.g. negation, non-finite marking, etc.)

Note all of the properties listed by the author describing pre and post-positions.

Gwords:

preposition gword (free order)

article gword (free order)

derived noun gword (root + derivational prefix): fixed order, no intervening elements, conventionalized meaning

possessor gword (free ordering & generally free combinations)